

Study of Equilibrium Constants of UO_2^{2+} -Malonic Acid Complexes at Various Ionic Strengths and in Dioxane-Water Mixtures

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Manuscript received 29 November 1977, accepted 17 May 1978

The equilibrium constants of UO_2^{2+} -malonic acid system in 20, 40, 60 and 80% (v/v) dioxane-water mixtures have been investigated by pH metric method at 0.032, 0.052, 0.072, 0.092 and 0.112 ionic strengths. It is observed that UO_2^{2+} forms 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with malonic acid in all solvent mixtures.

The distance of closest approach 'a' between the uranyl ion and malonic acid calculated for 1 : 1 complex in aqueous and 20% (v/v) dioxane-water mixture was found to be 4Å . The complexation equilibria for the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates :

are proposed. $pK/\log K$ values increase with increase in dioxane percentage.

THE stability of transition metal complexes with a great variety of ligands have been studied¹.

Uranyl complexes of dicarboxylic acids have been reported in the literature²⁻⁶. Rajan and Martell^{7,8} have thoroughly looked into the interactions of uranyl ion with organic ligands and correlated the stability constants of their chelates with the acid dissociation constants of the ligand acids. It is observed that uranyl ion forms 1 : 1 as well as 1 : 2 chelates with malonic acid in aqueous medium⁹. As a part of our studies^{10,11} on metal complexes with dicarboxylic acids, now we report uranyl complexes with malonic acid in dioxane-water mixtures. The present work was undertaken to examine (i) whether malonic acid can form 1 : 2 chelate in solvent mixtures with dielectric constants lower than water, (ii) the exact complexation equilibria of the complexes, (iii) inter ionic distance between the ligand and metal ion and (iv) the effect of dielectric constant on the stabilities.

Experimental

The chemicals used were Fluka products. Malonic acid obtained from Fluka (Germany) was purified by repeated crystallization. The concentration of uranyl ion was estimated by the standard procedure¹². All solutions were prepared in glass distilled water. The details regarding other chemicals, measurements of pH are given in an earlier paper^{13,14}.

The ionic strength of the solution was maintained by the addition of appropriate amounts of 1M sodium perchlorate solution. The calibration of

glass electrode in different solvent mixtures and conversion of B value (pH meter reading) into hydrogen ion concentration was done by the method of Van Uitert et al^{15,16}.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti^{17,18}. The accurate values of pK were calculated by pointwise calculations and are set out in Table 1. Initially $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were obtained by pointwise calculations since the

TABLE 1— pK VALUES OF MALONIC ACID IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS

μ	pK_1/pK_2	Temp. = 30°				
		Dioxane percentage (v/v)				
		0*	20	40	60	80
0.032	pK_1	5.59	6.37	7.38	8.28	10.07
	pK_2	2.83	3.29	3.93	4.85	7.05
0.052	pK_1	5.50	6.25	7.22	8.21	10.04
	pK_2	2.80	3.23	3.88	4.82	6.98
0.072	pK_1	5.47	6.22	7.19	8.16	9.99
	pK_2	2.73	3.18	3.85	4.80	6.96
0.092	pK_1	5.40	6.12	6.97	8.10	9.90
	pK_2	2.70	3.14	3.80	4.77	6.76
0.112	pK_1	5.30	6.08	6.79	8.05	9.87
	pK_2	2.68	3.10	3.74	4.74	6.69

* Values from Ref. 9

difference ($\log K_2 - \log K_1$) was less than 2, their accurate values were calculated by the method of least-squares (Table 2). The maximum value of \bar{n}

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TABLE 2—log K VALUES OF UO₂²⁺-MALONIC ACID COMPLEXES IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURE AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS

μ	log K ₁ /log K ₂	Dioxane percentage (v/v)				
		0*	20	40	60	80
0.032	log K ₁	5.87	6.42	8.61	11.11	14.72
	log K ₂	3.54	3.88	5.07	6.65	11.08
0.052	log K ₁	5.75	6.25	8.12	9.98	14.62
	log K ₂	3.66	4.07	5.18	6.80	11.12
0.072	log K ₁	5.71	6.12	7.82	9.69	14.46
	log K ₂	3.70	4.18	5.38	6.91	11.17
0.092	log K ₁	5.62	6.04	7.62	8.90	14.20
	log K ₂	3.76	4.36	5.40	6.96	11.20
0.112	log K ₁	5.56	5.98	7.41	8.85	14.16
	log K ₂	3.80	4.43	5.50	7.07	11.24

* Values from ref. 9

at each ionic strength was around 1.9. The formation of 1 : 2 complex was proved by the standard procedure¹⁹. The standard deviation of these values was between 0.01 and 0.05. A representative data, i.e., UO₂²⁺-malonic acid in 80% (v/v) dioxane-water mixture explain adequately the precision of the experimental work (Table 3).

TABLE 3—CALCULATIONS OF STABILITY CONSTANTS OF UO₂²⁺-MALONIC ACID. MEDIUM: 80% (v/v) DIOXANE-WATER

Temp. 30 ± 0.1°		μ = 0.11 M (NaClO ₄)		
B	$\bar{n}_{\text{expt.}}$	$\bar{n}_{\text{calcd.}}$	pL	Δ \bar{n}
2.0	0.373	0.370	15.064	0.002
2.2	0.503	0.525	14.681	-0.022
2.4	0.619	0.629	14.288	-0.010
2.6	0.662	0.655	13.896	0.007
3.6	1.343	1.388	11.939	0.005
3.8	1.486	1.482	11.551	0.004
4.0	1.568	1.540	11.168	0.028
4.2	1.698	1.690	10.771	0.008
4.4	1.758	1.742	10.376	0.011
Slope = 2.537 × 10 ²²		log K _{ML₁} = 14.176		
Intercept = 1.502 × 10 ¹⁴		log K _{ML₂} = 11.230		
Standard deviation : 0.014				

It was observed that at each percentage of dioxane, the values of pK₁, pK₂ and log K₁ decrease and log K₂ increase with the increase in ionic strength. The magnitude of the increment is, however, not the same for all dioxane-water mixtures. It is higher at the higher percentage of dioxane. The Bronsted equation²⁰

$$\log K = \log K^\circ + A\Delta z^2$$

and

$$pK = pK^\circ - A\Delta z^2$$

were used to determine the magnitude of Δz² in dioxane-water mixtures, where,

$$\Delta z^2 = z^2_{\text{product}} - z^2_{\text{reactants}}$$

The values of A and B at various percentages of dioxane-water mixtures at 30° were taken from the work of Harned and Owen²¹.

The plots of pK/log K against $\sqrt{\mu}$

A linear relationship between pK and log K against $\sqrt{\mu}$ was obtained for all percentages of dioxane-water mixtures for all the systems. The values of Δz² obtained from the slopes of these straight lines are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF Δz² OBTAINED FROM THE SLOPES

Reaction constant	Dioxane percentage (v/v)				Expected values on the basis of complex equilibria
	0	20	40	60	
pK ₁	2.24	1.72	1.09	0.24	2
pK ₂	3.87	2.70	2.94	0.61	4
log K ₁	3.87	4.52	7.94	7.09	-4
log K ₂	3.10	3.04	1.71	0.24	4

The observed Δz² are less than the expected values. The discrepancy between the two is significant at higher percentage of dioxane. An identical observation was recorded by Jahagirdar and Khanolkar for Cu²⁺-3, 5-dibromosalicylic acid²².

The pK/log K against $\sqrt{\mu}/1 + \sqrt{\mu}$ and $\sqrt{\mu}/1 + \sqrt{\mu} - 0.3\mu$ also gave linear plots without any improvement in the magnitude in Δz². The observed values thus are away from the expected ones. The discrepancy may be due to the fact that the value for 'a' was fixed at 3.3A°. It was, therefore, decided to calculate 'a' values in order to understand the discrepancy.

Calculation of accurate 'a' value

The most accurate value of 'a' can be calculated by method of successive approximations by putting different values of 'a' in the Bronsted and Christian²³ equation :

$$\log K = \log K^\circ + \frac{A\Delta z^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + B.a \sqrt{\mu}}$$

and observing its influence on the log K' against $\sqrt{\mu}$ plots. It is expected that for the correct value of 'a', log K° against $\sqrt{\mu}$ plot should be linear and parallel to the $\sqrt{\mu}$ axis. The calculations were made by taking the values of A and B as 0.5161 and 0.330 × 10²² respectively in water at 30^{±2}°. None of the plots (except for a = 4A°) is parallel to the $\sqrt{\mu}$ axis. It may, therefore, be concluded that the value of 'a' for UO₂²⁺-malonic acid in aqueous medium is 4A°. This was further confirmed from the plots of log K against $\sqrt{\mu}/1 + B.a \sqrt{\mu} = \sqrt{\mu}/1 + 1.3204 \sqrt{\mu}$ which gave the slope value -4.24 identical to the one expected for 1 : 1 complex for UO₂²⁺-malonate in 20% dioxane-water mixtures. It is observed that the values of 'a' remain constant in both the cases, i.e., 4A°.

The closest distance of approach between the metal ion and the ligand is given by the expression a = r₁ + r₂ - Δ, where r₁ and r₂ are the radii of a

cation and anion and Δ is penetration distance. The total size of the ligand molecule is roughly estimated from the knowledge of bond length and bond angles. In aqueous solution uranyl ion is present as hydrated ion and the total size of the ion was calculated by considering a unimolecular layer in the inner hydration sphere. The total size of hydrated uranyl ion being thus 3.93\AA , the magnitude of Δ would be 1.5\AA . This value arises because when anion and cation meet the anion penetrates in the hydration sheath of the cation by this distance. This penetration arises because of the attraction of a negatively charged ligand for a positively charged metal ion.

The nature of complexation equilibria

The interaction of uranyl ion with both the species, i.e., undissociated malonic acid (H_2L) and dissociated species (HL) is possible as pK_1 value of malonic acid is 2.68⁹. The formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates occur by the equilibria :

The magnitude of Δz^2 for the reactions (a) and (b) are -2 and -4 respectively. The calculated value from ionic parameters is -4.24 close to -4 . It is, therefore, concluded that the complexation is occurring by the equilibrium (b). In addition to this, in dioxane-water mixture the B values (pH meter readings) are around 3.0 at $\bar{n}=0.5$ for 20, 40, 60 and 80% (v/v) dioxane-water mixtures, the practical pK_1 values are 2.95, 3.40, 3.87 and 4.15 respectively. At $B=3.0$, the concentration of H_2L would therefore be greater than HL at higher percentage of dioxane. Finally at 80% of dioxane $[H_2L] \gg [HL]$. The complexation reactions 'a' and 'b' proceed at 20, 40, 60 while 'b' is prominent for the observed magnitude of Δz^2 , for 1 : 1 chelates.

Effect of dielectric constant on stabilities

In the system studied, the values of $pK/\log K$ increase with decrease in dielectric constant. The plots of $pK/\log K$ against $1/D$ were non-linear while those against mole fraction exhibit linearity. In the plots of pK vs $1/D$, the first three points invariably fell on a straight line.

Acknowledgement

Authors wish to thank Prof. K. A. Thakar, Head, Chemistry Department, Marathwada University for

his keen interest. One of us (DNS) thanks the C.S.I.R. for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

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